

“NEED OF IRRIGATION IN SOLAPUR DISTRICT: A GEOGRAPHICAL ANALYSIS”

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Abstract:

In this research paper an attempt is made to examine the relationship between irrigation and agriculture in Solapur district. Irrigation happens to be the key input for the development on agriculture. Solapur district is a drought prone area in western Maharashtra of India. In this block scanty water resource for protective irrigation is the factor controlling the agricultural development of this semi arid region. There are many irrigation facilities in this region like Ujjani, Nira river, canal, Kolegaon dam etc. Almost all area is flat with some small patches of hills which are located in the western part of Solapur district. Flat are suitable for irrigation development. The rainfall distributions highly uneven, hence irrigation is very essential for the development of agriculture in this area.

Keywords: irrigation, drought, arid, Ujjani, uneven

Introduction:

Economic backbone of India is moving around agriculture relation of water and agriculture is connected with each other. No other country in the world most probably developed its water resources with such intensity and vigor as India 65 million hectares of land were brought under irrigation during 1947 and 2000 ground water which was never tapped for large scale irrigation before, was explosion an huge scale.

Objectives:

The major objectives of the paper are to analyze the water resource and various type of irrigation methods are working in develop agriculture.

Study Region:

Present study deals with the geographical perspectives of the agriculture in Solapur district. This district is one of the largest districts in Maharashtra. The total areas of the district are 14895 sq.km. divided in the eleven tahsils. Out of total area of Maharashtra Solapur district has 4.45% which is commonly in drought prone area where irrigation playing important role in agriculture. The Solapur district lives between 17⁰05' North latitudes to 18⁰32' North latitudes and 74⁰42' East longitudes to 76⁰15' East longitudes. This district surrounding by Ahmednagar district to north, Osmanabad to NortEast, Karnataka state to the South East, Sangli Satara to the West.

Map No.1

Database and Methodology:

Present paper mostly reveals on the secondary data collected through Agricultural department and district statistical department of Maharashtra.

For this purpose present investigation district is selected as in general and every tahsil is particular. In first stage tahsilwise area is selected for this research.

Irrigation in Solapur District:

Irrigation has played an important role in transforming the rural landscape of the study region. Nira right bank canal Ujjani right left region bank canal and other water tanks like Ashti lake Ekruk lake sina kolegaon there are played a vital role in transforming the cropping pattern of the area. More ever entire economy has been influenced by the development of irrigation.

There are the major irrigation project namely Ujjani project and veer project. Ujjani project is on Bhima river new Ujjani village in Madha tahsil are provides irrigation to Madha, Mohol, Pandharpur, North Solapur, South Solapur, Mangalwedha and Malshiras. Veer dam is on the Neera river near Veer village in Pune district Malshiras, Sangola, and Pandharpur tahsils are irrigated by this canal.

Table No.1

Solapur District: Tahsilwise percentage of Land under irrigation by different sources

Sr. No.	Tahsils	Sources of Irrigation		
		Canal	Well	Other
1	North Solapur	-	9.88	1.86
2	Barshi	1.68	10.21	3.68
3	Akkalkot	-	11.71	2.46
4	South Solapur	4.85	5.59	2.38
5	Mohol	5.74	7.79	2.53
6	Mangalwdha	1.30	7.52	5.68
7	Pandharpur	12.47	11.11	10.19
8	Sangola	13.72	6.18	12.67
9	Malshiras	21.99	15.39	12.87
10	Karmala	22.48	8.75	25.49
11	Madha	11.47	17.87	6.14
	Total	95.70	112.00	85.95
	percentage	32.69	38.14	29.27

Source: Socio-Economic Review and statistical Abstracts, Solapur district, 2005-2006

The table No.1 shows that total land under canal is 32.69 percentage, 38.14 percentage land is under other well irrigation and 29.27 percentage land is under other sources of irrigation. Dominance of land irrigation is found in Malshiras, Karmala, Pandharpur and Sangola tahsils more area under well is observed in Madha, Malshiras and Pandharpur tahsils. Asti lake, Ekruk lake, Kolegaon and other medium project are

important. Karmala is dominant of the other irrigation which is left irrigation from the Ujjani back water.

Diagram No.1

Conclusion and Suggestions:

1. Solapur is drought prone area where a artificial irrigation is essential.
2. In this area canal is multipurpose way of irrigation this area. For the huge produce water needed.
3. Water in well is very useful method in the study area. These well are affected by canal irrigation.
4. Agricultural activities in Solapur district are still dependent on the several climatic condition.

In brief the object of irrigation is to argument from production. Irrigation thus occupying an important place in the development of agriculture. The region gets 75 percent rain from South West monsoon. The variability of rainfall is high in the western part than east part of the study area. The western part the variability in the annual rainfall from year is large. It indicates acute need of irrigation well, canals, rivers are used for irrigation and drip sprinkle, mataka system plays a very vital role as source irrigation in study area.

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